

Abstract

This article presents information about the life path and works of Muso Toshmuhammad oglu Oybek, a prominent figure in 20th century Uzbek literature. It discusses his creative achievements and literary contributions.

Keywords: Poetry, literature, poet, language, epic, sketch, epic poem, academy, historical, culture, national, classical

Introduction

Muso Toshmuhammad oglu Oybek is one of the prominent figures in Uzbek literature, leaving a significant legacy as a literary scholar, writer, poet, and translator. Through his creative work, he deeply reflected the history, culture, and social life of the Uzbek people, making a great contribution to the development of national literature. In Oybek's works, the ideas of humanity, compassion, and patriotism hold central importance. His novel "*Qutlug' qon*", poetry collections, and scholarly-critical articles have left an indelible mark on Uzbek literature. This article discusses Oybek's life, creative work, and his role in our literature.

Muso Toshmuhammad oglu Oybek, born on January 10, 1905, in Tashkent to a craftsman and weaver family, is one of the most prominent figures in Uzbek literature. He received his early education at the Oqmasjid neighborhood school from 1911 to 1917, then attended the "Namuna" school, organized by Munavvarqori Abdurashidhonov, from 1918 to 1921. Afterward, he continued his studies at the Navoiy Technical School of Education and Training from 1921 to 1925, and later at the Faculty of Social Sciences of Tashkent University from 1925 to 1927. He further studied at the Leningrad Institute of National Economy from 1927 to 1929. Due to a severe illness, he returned to Tashkent and completed his education at Tashkent University in 1930. Oybek, a poet, writer, literary scholar, and public figure, became a member of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan in 1943. After the death of Hamid Olimjon, he served as the Chairman of the Writers' Union and as the Chief Editor of the *Sharq Yulduzi* journal from 1945 to 1951. He was also the Director of the Institute of Language and Literature from 1950 to 1952 and the Chief Editor of the *Uzbek Language and Literature* journal from 1958 to 1968.

In the early 1950s, with the onset of the Stalinist repressions, Oybek suffered a stroke and passed away after a prolonged illness. Oybek began his literary career as a poet, publishing his first poem, "*Cholg'u tovushi*" (The Sound of Music), in the *Armug'on* journal in 1922. At that time, he was influenced by the poetry of Cholpon and the "young Ottomans," whose spirit reflected in his early works. In 1926, Oybek entered Uzbek literature with his poetry collection "*Tuyg'ular*" (Emotions). His epics such as "*Dilbar-davr qizi*" (The Beauty of the Age) in 1931, "*O'ch*" (The Flame) in 1932, "*Baxtigul va Sog'indiq*" (The Happy Gul and Longing) and "*Temirchi jo'ra*" (The Iron Friend) in 1933 are notable landmarks in the poetic

landscape of their time. In these epics, the poet not only created heroic images of his era but also raised important social and moral issues while delving into historical past themes.

Oybek's early lyrical-epic poetry experiments demonstrated his ability to create grand epic canvases. He created nearly twenty epics on both historical and contemporary subjects. His 1940 novel *"Qutlug' qon"* (Noble Blood) depicts the life of the peoples of Central Asia during World War I, and his 1943 novel *"Navoiy"* is dedicated to the life and work of the great Uzbek poet and philosopher, Alisher Navoi, and has been translated into several languages. Oybek's poems in *"Chimyon daftari"* (The Notebook of Chimyon) are among the finest examples of Uzbek lyric poetry, capturing the beauty and unique colors of Uzbek nature.

Despite being forced to create poems of "tragic poetry," in line with the state's political agenda, Oybek also wrote many poems and epics promoting the ideas of patriotism, labor, and national pride, such as *"O'zbekiston"* (Uzbekistan), *"Dneprostroy"*, *"Fanga yurish"* (Walk for Science), *"Raisa"*, and *"Qizlar"* (Girls) in the 1930s and 1940s. Oybek's *"Qizlar"* (Girls) epic, written in 1947, and other works, such as *"Hamza"* (1948), *"Zafar va Zahro"* (Victory and Zahro) in 1950, and *"Haqgo'yilar"* (True Believers) in 1952, contributed to the beginning of a new era in Uzbek poetry in the 1960s.

In the 1960s, despite his illness, Oybek continued to create pure lyrical works such as *"Davrim jarohati"* (Wounds of My Time), dedicated to the Hiroshima tragedy in 1952, and *"Guli va Navoiy"* (The Rose and Navoi) in 1968. He also began writing lyrical epics on Amir Timur and Babur. Oybek's prose legacy includes five novels: *"Qutlug' qon"*, *"Navoiy"*, *"Oltin vodiyan shabadalar"* (Breezes from the Golden Valley), *"Quyosh qoraymas"* (The Sun Will Not Darken), and *"Ulug' yo'l"* (The Great Path), along with four novellas: *"Shonli yo'l"* (The Glorious Path), *"Hyp qidirib"* (In Search of the Hyp), *"Bolalik xotiralarim"* (My Childhood Memories), and *"Bola Alisher"* (The Child Alisher), as well as several short stories and essays.

Oybek's first attempt in the novel genre was *"Qutlug' qon"*, written in 1938 during one of the most challenging periods of his life. This novel, published in 1940, captures the difficult life of the Uzbek people on the eve of World War I. The depiction of the widespread poverty and social unrest during this period, driven by colonial policies and the emerging capitalist relations in the region, paints a vivid picture of the collective struggle.

Oybek's contribution to Uzbek literature also extended to translation. He translated works of Pushkin, Lermontov, and Molière into Uzbek, enriching the Uzbek translation tradition. The Oybek Museum was established in his honor in 1980, and a monument was erected at his former residence. A metro station in Tashkent, as well as a drama theater in Qashqadaryo, carry his name, and he was posthumously awarded the "For Great Services" Order in 2001.

Conclusion

Muso Toshmuhammad o'g'lu Oybek is one of the great figures in Uzbek literature, whose creative legacy has made an invaluable contribution to the development of our national culture. His works are significant not only for their artistic excellence but also for shedding light on historical truths, promoting human virtues, and expressing national identity. The works of Oybek remain relevant to this day, and his novels, poems, and scholarly articles continue to serve as invaluable sources for new generations of readers. Therefore, it is essential for us to study his creative legacy and promote his works, further enriching our national literature.

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